

Exserted stigma showed higher receptivity within 1-2 d after flowering (see table). Seed set after pollination was in direct proportion to percentage exserted stigma (PES), and seed set was higher on spikelets with double exserted stigma than on those with single exserted stigma. With pollination the second day after flowering, seed set on spikelets with double and single exserted stigma was 0 in Xieqing-zao A, 20% in 25154, and 51% in 97154, indicating marked differences in stigma receptivity.

Receptivity was also closely associated with stigmatic characteristics. Stigma breadth was 0.36 mm in 25154 and 0.37 mm in 97154, but only 0.30 mm in Xieqing-zao. Xieqing-zao stigmas were slender and less branchy, easily damaged when protruded, and dried quickly after flowering, losing receptivity.

Percentage seed set on spikelets with

Exserted stigma and seed set under artificial pollination by day after flowering.^a Linshui, Hainan, China, 1984 spring.

Cultivar	Pollination day after flowering ^b	Spikelets (no.)	Exserted stigma (%)	Seed set (%) in spikelets			
				Total (exserted and nonexserted)	Exserted stigma	Double exserted stigma	Single exserted stigma
97154 sel.	Check	315	59.4	2.9	4.8	7.7	3.3
	Same day	241	63.9	45.6	71.4	70.5	71.8
	Day 1	217	68.2	32.3	47.3	80.0	35.2
	Day 2	240	62.9	32.1	51.0	72.5	43.2
25154 sel. (artificially emasculated)	Check	230	32.6	0	0	0	0
	Day 1	125	53.6	23.2	43.3	73.3	34.6
	Day 2	121	46.3	9.1	19.6	33.3	17.0
Xieqing-zao	Check	105	18.1	0	0	0	0
	Day 1	129	29.5	8.5	29.0	71.4	19.4
	Day 2	93	23.7	0	0	0	0
	Day 3	83	21.7	0	0	0	0

^aEr-jiu-qing had no seed set after pollination on the same day, day 1, and day 2. ^bCheck = no pollination.

exserted stigma 2 d after flowering may be used as an index of receptivity of exserted stigma. Stigma exertion makes

it possible to breed CMS lines with higher PES and to improve the outcrossing rate. □

Yield potential

Rice heterosis for panicle branching, spikelet number, and vascular bundle number

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Heterosis for 9 quantitative characters was assessed in crosses using 7 high density (HD)-grain parents (at least 30% of the grains having specific gravity greater than 1.20) and 2 low density (LD)-grain parents.

Estimates of overall degree and direction of heterosis were positive and significant for number of secondary branches, number of spikelets on secondary branches, and number of inner vascular bundle, indicating dominance of higher values (Table 1). Heterosis was negative for number of spikelets on tertiary branches and number of outer vascular bundles where genes of lower count dominated. Low or nonsignificant heterosis for other characters may be due to little genetic

Table 1. Overall parental and F₁ means and deviation for 9 quantitative yield characters. IRRI, 1988.

Character	Mean of parents (P)	Mean of F ₁ s (F ₁)	Overall heterosis (F ₁ -P)	LSD (0.05)
Primary branches (no.)	11.31	11.27	-0.04	0.25
Secondary branches (no.)	33.09	34.96	1.87	1.56
Tertiary branches (no.)	0.91	0.64	-0.27	0.29
Spikelets on primary branches (no.)	66.64	65.53	-1.11	2.79
Spikelets on secondary branches (no.)	113.40	120.74	7.34	7.29
Spikelets on tertiary branches (no.)	2.40	1.44	-0.96	0.86
Total spikelets (no.)	182.30	187.74	5.44	8.21
Inner vascular bundles (no.)	23.12	23.98	0.86	0.52
Outer vascular bundles (no.)	23.43	21.94	-1.49	0.86

interactions or differences among parents.

Values for individual F₁ families differed from overall estimates for different characters, showing positive, negative, or no heterosis (Table 2). The F₁ means deviated conspicuously from parental and midparental values, indicating involvement of nonadditive gene action in the expression of most characters.

Substantial heterosis in the desirable direction was observed in number of primary branches, number of spikelets on primary branches, inner vascular

bundles, and outer vascular bundles. Three crosses among HD-grain parents and one cross between HD- and LD-grain parents exhibited positive heterosis for number of primary branches. The cross P2/P9 manifested positive heterosis for all other characters. Positive heterosis for total number of spikelets was observed in all crosses except P3/P8, through spikelet numbers on primary, secondary, and tertiary branches. Number of inner vascular bundles exhibited positive heterosis in most crosses, but the reverse was true for number of outer vascular bundles.

As panicles with more primary branches accommodate more HD grains, substantial heterosis for that

character may lead to higher yield. The three crosses with IR30 (P2) as a common parent in either direction

(P5/ P2, P1 / P2, and P2/ P9) had positive heterosis for panicles with more primary branches. □

Table 2. Heterosis percentage of 9 quantitative yield characters. IRRI, 1988.

Character	Heterosis (%) in given cross ^a							LSD (0.05)
	P1/P2 (HD/HD)	P3/P4 (HD/HD)	P5/P2 (HD/HD)	P2/P6 (HD/HD)	P4/P7 (HD/HD)	P3/P8 (HD/LD)	P2/P9 (HD/LD)	
Primary branches	5.21	1.69	9.42	-1.38	-7.23	-9.31	3.35	1.82
Secondary branches	0	9.77	4.75	6.00	23.63	-5.93	35.34	6.75
Tertiary branches	-39.39	-80.95	-100.00	11.11	80.00	12.00	150.00	27.00
Spikelets on primary branches	13.64	1.31	15.36	-7.49	-18.48	-2.38	4.25	3.66
Spikelets on secondary branches	0.67	11.78	4.89	15.63	32.85	-2.33	28.69	6.83
Spikelets on tertiary branches	-56.96	-88.73	-100.00	33.33	62.50	-18.99	122.00	19.70
Total spikelets	3.50	5.90	7.92	6.09	11.82	-2.67	19.51	3.12
Inner vascular bundles	4.86	2.15	1.07	1.73	-1.39	-0.44	9.33	1.68
Outer vascular bundles	1.79	-4.81	-11.34	-1.37	-11.24	-1.38	3.27	2.38

^aP1 = IR32307-75-1-3-1, P2 = IR30, P3 = IR34615-75-1-1, P4 = IR29725-135-2-2-3, P5 = IR29692-117-1-2-2, P6 = IR35337-61-2-2-2, P7 = IR28211-43-1-1-1-2, P8 = IR32419-102-3-2-3, P9 = IR32385-37-3-3-3.

Influence of silicon and its antagonists on rice mitochondria

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Silicon is beneficial to rice plant growth and development, but the mechanisms of its biological activity are obscure.

Si physiological antagonists As and Ge suppress rice plant growth and dry matter accumulation and induce necrosis. We studied rice mitochondria morphology to test the assumption that Si can stabilize and As and Ge can damage the energy-producing systems of the rice cells.

Rice variety Krasnodarsky 424 seedlings were grown to the 2-leaf stage in water culture, with 60 μmol Si in treatment 1, 60 μmol Ge in treatment 2, and 60 μmol As in treatment 3. Mitochondria were isolated with the sediments in 0.05 M tris-HCl; 0.01 M EDTA; 0.05% cystein (pH 7.4) buffer. The isolated mitochondria were fixed with gluteraldehyde and osmiate, contrasted with uranylacetate, stained

Mitochondrion in treatment with 60 μmol Si (a) and 60 μmol Ge (b), and destruction of spherical mitochondrion (c).

with Pb-citrate, and studied under an electron microscope.

Mitochondria in the Si treatment were almost uniform, spherical particles 0.2-0.5 μm in diameter (see figure). Mitochondria in the Ge suspension were about 50% smaller and elongated. Material of different electron densities distributed sporadically on the surface can be explained as either injury of